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***Haloxylon Scoparium*: An Ethnopharmacological Survey, Phytochemical Screening and Antibacterial Activity against Human Pathogens Causing Nosocomial Infection**

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Abstract. Nosocomial infections occur worldwide, both in the developed and developing world. They are a major cause of death and increased morbidity in hospitalized patients. This study deals with the valorization of medicinal plants of southwest Algeria, in order to find new bioactive natural products against human pathogens causing nosocomial infection.

Haloxylon Scoparium (Chenopodiaceae family) is a local medicinal plant, which has been used extensively in the southwestern part of Algeria. It was subjected to an ethnopharmacological survey, phytochemical screening and anti-nosocomial activity. The ethnopharmacological survey revealed that the *H. Scoparium* is used to treat numerous human diseases especially the infectious one such as skin infections, urinary and genital infections. Therefore, the *H. scoparium* aerial part was subjected to a phytochemical screening. Then its crude extracts, including, acetone, ethanol, methanol, chloroform, dichloromethane, chlorohydric and water extracts were tested against three pathogens causing nosocomial infection using the disc diffusion method. As a result, all the phytochemical constituents were found to be present in the aerial part of *H. scoparium*. The methanolic extract was found more bioactive comparing to the other extracts.

Key Words: Nosocomial infection, *Haloxylon scoparium*, ethnopharmacological survey, phytochemical screening, antibacterial activity,

Introduction

Nosocomial infections occur worldwide and affect both developed and resource-poor countries. Infections acquired in health care settings are among the major causes of death and increased morbidity among hospitalized patients [1,2]. They are a significant burden both for the patient and for public health. The organisms that cause nosocomial infections are often drug resistant. Many strains of *pneumococci*, *staphylococci*, *enterococci*, and *tuberculosis* are currently resistant to most or all antimicrobials which were once effective [3].

Algeria's distinctive morphology, varied topography and under changing climatic conditions permits the grow of more than 3000 plants species [4,5]. The south Algerian flora is very rich and a great number of species has been used traditionally for the treatment of several diseases without any scientific background [6]. Of the shrub and tree species encountered in the desert of southwest

Algeria, *Haloxylon Scoparium*, which is known locally as “Remth”, is one of the most used species traditionally in ethnomedicine.

H. scoparium Pomel [= *Hammada scoparia* (Pomel) Iljin., *Arthrophytum scoparium* (Pomel) Iljin., *Salsola articulata* Cav., *Haloxylon articulatum* (Cav.)], belongs to the family *chenopodiaceae*, which has 120 genera and more than 1700 species [7,8]. They are worldwide distributed especially in desert and semi desert areas in soils containing much salt. The plants are herbs, shrubs, subshrubs and rarely small trees [9].

Materials and methods

Ethnopharmacological survey

The traditional uses of *Haloxylon Scoparium* plant information were collected from different places in southwest Algeria generally (Naama, Tindouf and Adrar) and in Bechar region particularly.

The ethnobotanical data was collected between June 2010 and July 2011, based mainly on semi-structured questionnaires and open-ended conversations with selected more than 50 informants (Traditional Medical Practitioners) of different age, gender, occupation, education, and class. They included more than 39 men and 11 women, aged between 40 and 79 years. Interviews and discussions were conducted in the Arabic language, the common local language in the study area.

Plant material

The aerial part of *Haloxylon Scoparium* were collected from Boukais area (about 265 km of Bechar, southwest Algeria). The sample was air-dried under the shed at room temperature, then manually powdered and kept in polyethylene bags until used.

Preparation of extracts

The powdered aerial part of *Haloxylon scoparium* (50g) was extracted using seven different solvents with different polarities namely: water, acetone, ethanol, methanol, chloroform, dichloromethane and chloride acid 5%. The extracts was then filtered and concentrated in a rotary evaporator completely. Residues were kept in a hermetically closed color glass vial at 4°C until using.

Phytochemical screening

Standard screening test was carried out for various plant constituents. The plant material were screened for the presence or absence of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, steroids, phenols, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and anthraquinones by qualitative chemical analysis as per the guidelines of Sofowara (1993), Trease and Evans (1989) and Harborne (1973).

- *Test for alkaloids*

Mayer's test: A 50 mg of the plant material was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid. Solution was clarified by filtration. Filtrate was tested with Mayer's reagents. The treated solutions were observed for any precipitation.

- *Test for steroidal compounds*

Salkowski's test: 0.5 g of the plant material was dissolved in 2 ml chloroform in a test tube. Concentrated sulfuric acid was carefully added on the wall of the test tube to form a lower layer. A reddish brown color at the interface indicated the presence of a steroid ring.

Lieberman's test: 0.5 g of the plant material was dissolved in 2 ml of acetic anhydride and cooled well in an ice-bath. Concentrated sulfuric acid was then carefully added. A color change from purple to blue to green indicated the presence of a steroid nucleus.

- *Test for phenolic compounds*

100 mg of the plant material was dissolved in water. Few crystals of ferric sulfate were added to the mixture. Formation of dark-violet color indicated the presence of phenolic compounds.

- *Test for flavonoids*

Test for free flavonoids: Five milliliters of ethyl acetate was added to a solution of 0.5 g of the plant material in water. The mixture was shaken, allowed to settle and inspected for the production of yellow color in the organic layer, which is taken as positive for free flavonoids.

Reaction with sodium hydroxide: Dilute sodium hydroxide solution was added to a solution of 0.5 g of the plant material in water. The mixture was inspected for the production of yellow color which considered as positive test for flavonoids.

- *Test for saponins*

Froth test: 0.5 g of the plant material was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water in a test tube. The test tube was stoppered and shaken vigorously for about 30 seconds. The test tube was allowed to stand in a vertical position and observed over a 30 minute period of time. If a "honey comb" froth above the surface of liquid persists after 30 min. The sample is suspected to contain saponins.

- *Test for tannins*

Ferric chloride test: A portion of the plant material was dissolved in water. The solution was clarified by filtration. 10% ferric chloride solution was added to the clear filtrate. This was observed for a change in color to bluish black.

Formaldehyde test: To a solution of about 0.5 g of the plant material in 5ml water, 3 drops of formaldehyde and 6 drops of dilute hydrochloric acid were added. The resulting mixture was heated to boiling for 1 minute and cooled. The precipitate formed (if any) was washed with hot water, warm alcohol and warm 5% potassium hydroxide successively. A bulky precipitate, which leaves a colored residue after washing, indicated the presence of phlobatannins.

- *Test for anthraquinones*

Borntrager's test (Test for free anthraquinones): The hydro-alcoholic extract of the plant material (equivalent to 100 mg) was shaken vigorously with 10 ml of benzene, filtered and 5 ml of 10% ammonia solution added to the filtrate. Shake the mixture and the presence of a pink, red or violet color in the ammonia (lower) phase indicated the presence of free anthraquinones.

Modified Borntrager's test (Test for O-anthraquinone glycosides): For combined anthraquinones, 5 g of the plant extract was boiled with 10 ml 5% sulphuric acid for 1 hour and filtered while hot. The filtrate was shaken with 5 ml benzene; the benzene layer separated and half its own volume of 10% ammonia solution added. The formation of a pink, red or violet color in the ammonia phase (lower layer) indicated the presence of anthraquinone derivatives in the extract.

Microorganisms and preparation of bacterial suspension

Tree pathogenic nosocomial infection causing bacterial isolates, viz., *Staphylococcus aureus* (urinary infection), *Proteus mirabilis* (from skin) and *Escherichia coli* (urinary infection) were used during the present study and were obtained from Boujemaa Tourabi hospital (240 bed); Bechar district.

The bacterial culture strain was cultured in nutrient broth at 37°C and maintained on nutrient agar slant at 4°C. The previously identified microorganism was inoculated at 35 ± 2°C for 10 hours. A loop of pure slant culture is mixed with sterilized distilled water in a test tube under aseptic condition and content was thoroughly mixed to form a uniform suspension

Determination of antimicrobial activity (disc diffusion method)

For determination of antimicrobial potential of plant extract in different solvents against the selected microorganisms, the zone of inhibition using a modified agar diffusion method were used [10]. Bacterial strains grown on nutrient agar at 37°C for 18 h were suspended in saline solution (0.9% NaCl) and the suspension was used to inoculate. A sterile paper discs were impregnated with 40 µl of the extract and were placed on the inoculated agar. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Antibacterial activities were evaluated by measuring the inhibition zone diameters. The experiments were conducted in triplicate and the zones inhibition was measured in mm.

Results and discussion

The fieldwork was conducted in several places in Southwest Algeria (especially Bechar province) between June 2010 and July 2011. The information was contributed by more than 50 informants included more than 39 men and 11 women, aged between 40 and 79 years. It is evident from the interviews conducted in different places; knowledge of medicinal plants generally and *H. Scoparium* particularly is limited to traditional healers, herbalists and elderly persons due to lack of interest among the younger generation.

As it's shown in **Table 1**, traditional healers are using the *Haloxylon Scoparium* plant to cure some infectious diseases, such as urinary and genital infections as well as to cure diseases related to skin problems (eczema, wounds and sepsis, itching, burns), rheumatism, diabetes, cancer, infertility problems, hair problems, Antitoxin, Stomach ache, pregnancy Disorders, and poison (snake, scorpion and insect). Among the different plant parts, the aerial part was most frequently used for the treatment.

Table 1. Ethnopharmacological Survey of *H. Scoparium*

Area	Parts Used	Medicinal use
Bechar, Boukais, Moughel, Beni Abbas, Abadela, Taghit	Aerial part	Rheumatism, diabetes, cancer, urinary and genital infections, eczema, infertility, disorders of pregnancy, hair problems, stomach, wounds and sepsis, itching, burns, antitoxin, snake bite and scorpion sting
Naama, Mechria, Ain Safra	Aerial part	Urinary and genital infections, eczema, hair falling, wounds and sepsis.
Adrar	Aerial part	Urinary and genital infections, eczema, wounds, snake bite and scorpion sting
Tindouf	Whole plant	Eczema, wounds and sepsis, snake bite and scorpion sting

Phytochemical screening

The phytochemical screening was done using color forming and precipitating chemical reagents on the aerial part of *H. Scoparium* to generate preliminary data on the constituents of the plant. The results obtained from the tests were summarized in the following table.

Table 2. Phytochemical screening of the aerial part of *H. Scoparium*

Test	Reagents	Aerial Part
Alkaloids	Mayer's test	+
Steroidal compounds	Salkowski's test	+
	Lieberman's test	+
Phenolic compounds	Ferric sulfate	+
Flavonoids	Ethyl acetate	+
	Sodium hydroxide	+
Saponins	Froth test	+
Tannins	Ferric chloride	+
	Formaldehyde	+
Anthraquinones	Borntrager's test	+
	Modified Borntrager's test	+

The preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis of the *H. Scoparium* was carried out for detection of secondary metabolites and results indicate that all the phytochemical constituents were found to be present including: Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenols, and steroids.

Alkaloids are known to contain many pharmacological properties. They are mostly used as antidepressant, stimulants, anaesthetic, antitumor, antimalaria, antibacterial and amoebicide [11]. Flavonoids are known to have anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, antiviral, antispasmodic and diuretic effect [12,13], while Saponins are known to be immune booster. Extracts of plants, rich in saponins, are said to demonstrate anti-inflammatory, homolytic, allelopathic, cholesterol lowering and anticancer properties [14].

Tannins are good antimicrobial agent, which precipitate protein thereby providing waterproof layer on the skin when used externally or protect the underlying layers of the skin and limit the loss of fluid. They were found also to have antiviral, antibacterial, antiparasitic effects, anti-inflammatory, antiulcer and antioxidant property for possible therapeutic applications [15,16].

Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial activity of the different extracts of *H. Scoparium* (water, acetone, ethanol, methanol, chloroform, dichloromethane and chloride acid 5%) was investigated against nosocomial infection causing bacterial isolates viz., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Escherichia coli*. The inhibition zone, measured in millimeters, including the diameter of the paper disk, was used as the criterion for measuring the antibacterial activity of *H. Scoparium*.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of *H. Scoparium* extracts

Extract	<i>S. Aureus</i>	<i>E. Coli</i>	<i>P. Mirabilis</i>
Acetone extract	6	6	6
Methanol extract	15	13	17
Ethanol extract	6	12	9
Chloroform extract	6	7	6
Dichloromethane extract	6	6	6
HCl (5%) extract	7	12	7
Water extract	6	6	6

The Methanolic crude extract show the higher degree of inhibitory activity against *P. Mirabilis* with the mean growth inhibition zone of 17mm, than the *staphylococcus aureus* 15mm and 13mm with *E. Coli* respectively. Chlorohydric and ethanolic extracts were found to be bioactive showing the maximum zone of inhibition 12mm against the *E. Coli*, rather than the other test organisms. Whereas, acetones, dichloromethane and water extracts showed no activity against all the tested germs. Briefly, this results show that *H. Scoparium* has several activities against the three tested bacteria; which means that the alkaloids, the saponosides, flavonoids and tannin may be the major bioactive substances in this plants. Among the various solvents tested, the methanol extract showed more inhibitory activity when compared to other solvent extracts.

Conclusion

The growing incidences of drug-resistant pathogens have increased the attention on several medicinal plants and their metabolites for antimicrobial properties. A conducted ethnopharmacological survey revealed that the *H. Scoparium* is used to treat numerous human diseases especially the infectious one such as skin infections, urinary and genital infections.

To search for a compound, which elicits a particular bioactive response, an appropriate assay is required to screen the source material, and to monitor extracts there from and subsequent purification steps. Therefore, a preliminary study of *H. Scoparium* was done to generate preliminary data on the phyto-constituents of this plant and to choose the most bioactive extract among seven extracts tested.

Thus, the present study reveals that the *H. Scoparium* contains the important bioactive compound and secondary metabolite with antimicrobial potential against human pathogens causing nosocomial infection. The antimicrobial potential of the plant may be attributed to the various bioactive compounds present in the crude extracts. The purified compound may be more potential and significant against the selected microorganism. Further studies require isolation and individual characterization of each bioactive compound for the pharmaceutical use.

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